

The Other World in B.R. Collins' *Game Runner* (2011)

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In *Game Runner* (2011), the alternative world existing parallel to the primary world takes the shape of a virtual reality, simulated by a computer into an immersive multimedia. *Game Runner* comes from a long, diverse line of children's books featuring the virtual gamespace; for example, Raymond Abrashkin and Jay William's *Danny Dunn, Invisible Boy* (1974), Gillian Rubinstein's *Space Demons* (1986), and one that I know well is Terry Pratchett's *Only You Can Save Mankind* (1992), where the protagonist goes into the game to save the aliens instead of shooting them. Interestingly, both *Space Demons* and *OYCSM* use virtual reality and gamespace to examine the issue of war, and although *Game Runner* is not on war, Rick still engages in one-to-one combat, and like almost all games, the notion that all other players and the game itself are your adversaries is maintained. You have to keep fighting to keep winning and this also contributes to that sense of being immersed in the game. My point is that, the game, or rather the advanced technology in game software has enabled the creation of another world as well as another party to interact with, so much so that Rick is completely immersed in it.

Marie-Laure Ryan, in an article on virtual reality writes that

the user of a VR system interacts with a world that is experienced as existing autonomously because this world is accessible to many senses, particularly to the sense of touch... As a relation involving the body, the interactivity of VR immerses the user in an [sic] world already in place; as a process involving the mind, it turns the user's relation to this world into a creative membership. (Ryan; web)

Rick's interactivity with the gamescape, resulting in his immersion in it, owes to three qualities of a virtual reality; speed, range, and mapping, as outlined by Jonathan Steuer. Speed enables faster response, which is in direct correlation with faster action and changes in real time; range refers to the choice of actions available, making the gamescape more "malleable" (Ryan); and mapping refers to "the ability of a system to map its controls to changes in the mediated environment in a natural and predictable manner" (Steuer qtd. in Ryan).

Rick's immersion in and interactivity with the gamescape is to the extent that it becomes his primary world, making the world outside the game his alternative world. If I were to put it in a hierarchy, Rick's primary world is the game, the Crater compound is his secondary other world, and his other *other* world is the world outside the compound, the dystopian London called Undone, suffering from "Alternative Energy Source pollution and nuclear disasters" (Collins 89). With that level of immersion, Rick is no longer just role-playing in an RPG. The virtual Rick running the maze is who he is as a person, because after every session, he does not go to be anything else. He goes to sleep and eat so that he could play again, sessions after sessions, and he has an infinite account. It is his job, but that's merely an understatement. The virtual Rick and the flesh-and-blood Rick are almost interchangeable, almost the same person; even outside the game he thinks in game terms.

The book problematises the advance of human civilisation in terms of science and technology; firstly, despite all these sophisticated technology, Rick has limited knowledge of the company, the game, Daed, what happens outside, or even himself. We never really know if Daed is telling the truth about adopting or loving Rick. Whatever he tells Rick are all stories that only secures his position in Crater.

Secondly, the book brings in the struggle between logic and reason. Computer systems work on the binary of 0 and 1; its language is entirely numbers and its operation is logical. Rick's immersion in the Maze makes him a logical person; if he sees a corpse, he loots it. To get through a succession of blades, he calculates the intervals. Even his usefulness to Daed is logical; as long as he does what Daed tells him to do, Daed treats him well. It's actually mechanical and almost automatic. But once Rick gets cut out of the game, he has to learn that human-game logic is not applicable to human-human relationship. Stealing Asterion from Perdita to give it to Daed is logical but he learns the hard way that it is not reasonable; Asterion in Daed's hands later leads to Perdita's murder, and Daed's suicide. Although Daed now is immortal inside the game, he cuts off all communications with Rick, leaving Rick all alone. At the end of the book, breaking out of the Crater compound is not logical when Rick's life and safety are guaranteed there, but he has reasons now – he needs to escape and find out about things he does not know because what he currently knows, i.e. the Maze, the iTank, Crater, and Daed have all collapsed.

Given the contemporariness of the virtual world in *Game Runner*, it is interesting how it makes use of Greek mythology. In fact, the book is a re-writing of the story of Daedalus and Icarus. On one hand it reflects the postmodern literary practice of intertextuality, and on the other, perpetuates the intersection of classical antiquity and science fiction which has been employed since Mary Shelley's *Frankenstein* (1818), with its subtitle *the Modern Prometheus* (Rogers and Stevens 2015). In the original myth, Daedalus was a craftsman and his most prominent creation was the labyrinth at King Minos' Knososs Palace in Crete. He was Icarus' father, and depending on versions, had a nephew named Perdix. After building the labyrinth, Daedalus and Icarus were imprisoned by King Minos in a tower to preserve

the secret of the labyrinth. Daedalus made artificial wings using feathers and wax for him and Icarus, telling his son not to fly too close to the sun because it would melt the wax. Icarus did, fell into the sea and died. Interestingly, Daedalus lamented for the failure of the wings more than for the death of Icarus. As an uncle to Perdix, Daedalus was so jealous of Perdix's intelligence and saw him as a rival for his crafts. He killed Perdix by pushing him off a tower.

With *Game Runner*, Collins dismantles and re-writes the myth. We discover that Daed's full name is Daedalus, and he works with Crater, echoing Crete in the myth. His son, Rick, is a semi-anagram on Icarus and Rick indeed gets to fly both in the Maze and even more realistically when he plays in the iTank. At the end of the story, Rick gains full resemblance to Icarus when his shirt melts in the fire from the explosion, "leaving two terrible burns: symmetrical, running the whole length of his back, like wings" (262). Daed kills Perdita, the best Creative in Crater by pushing her off level 20 of the Crater building. Asterion in Greek mythology has several references but the closest to the book Asterion is the minotaur in the labyrinth that Daedalus had created for King Minos. In the book, using the Asterion programme, Daed is able to transport his consciousness into the game, where he now is immortal and so, is dead-less, a word play on his name. Even Herkules404, the game runner that Rick has to defeat alludes to the Greek Hercules, fitting his ability to defeat the game, and his ghost-ness is signified by the 404, like the HTTP 404 code that we get when the link we click is missing.

Collins also dismantles the original story by giving a voice and agency to Icarus via Rick. Rick manages to escape from Crater and its capitalistic manipulation on people and the game industry. Daed has escaped too, but perhaps only partly, because he is now virtually immortal in the iTank software and thus is still under

Crater. Icarus' wings led to his downfall, but Rick gains his 'wings' after the fall, his act of escape is in direct disobedience to Daed's order not to leave Crater. If Icarus flew too close to the sun, perhaps mesmerised by it, Rick falls to the world outside to which he has initially planned to escape. Collins' giving a voice to Icarus via Rick is an act of empowerment; for Rick, he is now able to decide for himself and he decides to break away.

Marie-Laure Ryan also remarks that

Immersion in a virtual world is viewed by most theorists of postmodernism as a passive subjection to the authority of the world-designer--a subjection exemplified by the entrapment of tourists in the self-enclosed virtual realities of theme parks or vacation resorts (where the visitor's only freedom is the freedom to use his credit card). (Ryan)

Viewed in this term, if Rick's immersion in the games manufactured by Crater is a passive subjection, Rick's escape from the Crater compound therefore becomes his active anarchy towards the company and its capitalistic endeavours in how they manufacture games that are so immersive and endless so that people will keep playing and paying. It is only by disengaging himself from the game and escaping out of the compound that Rick is able to gain agency and form his own understanding of the world around him, which is further explored in the sequel, *Maze Cheat*.

Clare Bradford et al. (2008; 201) categorise virtual reality narratives with the spectrum of posthumanism and suggest that a prominent question raised is the interrogation of what it means to be human and views of the future. They remark that most of these works are set within a

a recognisable representation of a 'real' world, but by breaching the boundaries between the virtual and the real they raise questions about the relationships between the lived embodied, or materiality instantiated, world of experiences and the virtual reality of information. (Bradford et al. 171)

The world in *Game Runner* is a bleak one suffering from the aftermath of energy source crises but I would like to think that Rick embodies a notion of hope in how he dares to break away and endeavours to dismantle the company by playing the game they have created.

Mark Zuckerberg optimistically remarks that “[v]irtual reality was once the dream of science fiction” (qtd. in Hern; web) but this year, devices enabling virtual reality like Oculus Rift, HTC Vive, and PlayStation VR will be sold and then be happily bought by consumers. Is this then just the start of the iTank where at one point, you can transfer your consciousness and live forever in the gamespace, or is it simply a milestone in human civilisation? Where do we draw the line between the realities if the virtual one is highly immersive and interactive? Do we need to? As sci-fi, the story explores projected changes in scientific knowledge and its relation to human consumers sometime in the far future, how it influences, shapes, improves or endangers our lives. The other world in 21st century children’s books in *Game Runner* gives a glimpse into a future that we might be already heading for; one with advanced technology, advanced virtual reality but is seriously declining in terms of human touch and being human. It is not happening now but is firmly grounded in the now in terms of the advance in science and technology as well as the ecological decline. The virtual reality in *Game Runner* functions as a foil to our primary reality, a medium for social commentary and criticism, as well as a site for empowerment for

those who are otherwise powerless. It reflects the concerns of today's society and as a children's book, interrogates parent-child relationship, child's subjectivity and agency, the issue of compromised childhood, and the overall childhood experience against the background of progress in science and technology in the 21st century.

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